

Solvent Extraction of Mercury(II) with Rhodamine B into Nitrobenzene

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The toxicity of mercury and its harmful effects on plants, animals and human beings are well documented¹. It is apparent that a rapid and selective method for the separation of Hg^{II} from other elements is required. The reagent rhodamine B² has been used for the extraction of W^{VI}, Mo^{VI}, Zn^{II}, Sc^{III}, Re^{VII} and Tc^{VII}. However, rhodamine B has not been used for the solvent extraction of Hg^{II}. The present work describes a method for the solvent extraction and radiochemical separation of Hg^{II} employing rhodamine B reagent. ²⁰³Hg was used as a tracer.

Results and Discussion

The extraction coefficient value (Table 1) revealed a maximum *E* value of 448 at a pH of 2.0. The percentage extraction was found to be greater than 99.0% in the pH range 2.0–5.0. The *E* value was found to decrease in the more basic range (Table 1). The reproducibility of the method was found to be 6.16%. The percentage extraction was found to be maximum for an equilibration time of 4.0 min under the experimental conditions.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF pH AND TIME OF EQUILIBRATION

pH	Extraction coefficient (<i>E</i>)	Time of equilibration min
2.0	135	1.0
2.0	317	2.0
2.0	343	3.0
2.0	448	4.0
2.0	354	5.0
2.5	323	4.0
3.0	288	4.0
4.0	216	4.0
5.0	108	4.0
6.0	53	4.0
7.0	24	4.0
8.0	2.15	4.0
9.0	0.014	4.0
10.0	0.005	4.0

Of the solvents studied, the *E* value was found to be maximum for nitrobenzene. The extraction coefficient value (*E* in parenthesis) revealed a decreasing trend : nitrobenzene (448) > iso-butylmethylketone (135) > *o*-dichlorobenzene (55) > 1,2-dichlorobenzene (49) > nitromethane (13) > chloroform (11) = amylacetate (11) > ethylacetate (10) > 1-pentanol (2.0) > 1-heptanol (1.5) = 1-octanol (1.5) > ben-

zene (1.0) > toluene (0.31) > xylene (0.17) > hexane (0.003) > heptane (0.002) > cyclohexane (0.001) = carbon tetrachloride (0.001). After equilibration no phase separation was observed for iso-propanol, pyridine, methyl ethylketone and ethylene glycol.

Effect of foreign ions : The effect of sodium, potassium or ammonium salts on the extraction coefficient value revealed that 100 mg of iodide, EDTA, sulphate, iodate, hypophosphite, fluoride, acetate, borate, chloride, phosphate, tartrate, bromide and citrate; 25 mg of sulphite; 10 mg of tungstate and oxalate do not decrease the *E* value of Hg^{II}. Nitrite, nitrate, cyanide, sulphide and thiocyanate lowered the *E* value of Hg^{II}. The interference was removed by expelling with conc. HCl. The interference of thiosulphate, thiourea and bromate was removed by decomposing with aqua regia; excess of nitrate was expelled with conc. HCl. Chromate and dichromate were reduced with conc. HCl and H₂O₂. Of the cations studied, Rb^I, Co^{II}, Na^I, Mn^{II}, Sc^{III}, La^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ir^{IV}, Cr^{III}, Zr^{IV}, Ca^{II}, P^V, Cl^I, Cs^I, As^{III}, Ce^{III}, Se^{IV}, Ce^{IV}, Eu^{III}, Tl^I and Sr^{II} were extracted to the extent of less than 1.0%. Fe^{II}, K^I, Zn^{II}, In^{III}, Sb^{III}, Sn^{IV}, Cd^{II}, Ba^{II}, S^{VI} and Fe^{III} were extracted between 1 and 10%. Sb^V, W^{VI}, Sn^{II}, Ru^{III}, Mo^{VI}, Ag^I, Pd^{II}, Cr^{VI}, Au^{III}, Re^{VII} and Tc^{VII} were extracted more than 10%. The percentage extraction of the interfering elements such as Sb^V and W^{VI} was reduced to 0.5% and 0.9% respectively, by masking Sb^V with 100 mg of tartrate and precipitating W^{VI} as tungstic acid with HCl. The interference of Sn^{II} was lowered to 4.9% by oxidising Sn^{II} to Sn^{IV} with HNO₃. The excess of nitrate was expelled with conc. HCl. The percentage extraction of metal ions such as Ru^{III}, Ag^I, Pd^{II} and Au^{III} was reduced to less than 2% by precipitating Ru^{III} as metal with SO₂ water, Ag^I as AgCl with NaCl, Pd^{II} as PdI₂ with KI and Au^{III} as metal with hydroquinone. The extraction of Mo^{VI} and Cr^{VI} was brought down to 7.3% and 0.2% respectively, by masking Mo^{VI} with H₂O₂ and reducing Cr^{VI} to Cr^{III} by boiling with HCl and H₂O₂. The interference of Re^{VII} and Tc^{VII} was decreased to 5.6% and 7.5% respectively, by masking with hydroxylamine hydrochloride.

The stoichiometry of the extracted species was determined by the method of substoichiometric extraction. A plot of amount of Hg^{II} taken vs the activity of the organic aliquot gave a linear relationship until it was sub-equivalent to the reagent added, after which it remained constant. A break occurred at the substoichiometry of Hg^{II}: rhodamine B in the ratio of 1 : 2. The stoichiometry of

metal-to-reagent was further supported by the slope-ratio method and solid complex analysis.

A 1.0 mg of Hg^{II} was back-extracted to better than 99% with 20 ml of 1:1 ammonia solution.

Experimental

All the chemicals and reagents used were of A.R. grade. HgCl_2 was used to prepare the stock solution of Hg^{II} . ^{203}Hg and the isotopes used for studying the cation interference were provided by B.R.I.T., Trombay. Solutions of the cations and anions were prepared by dissolving the appropriate salts in distilled water. Acid was added wherever necessary and these solutions were standardised³. Rhodamine B was used as such.

The isotopes were counted such that β -emitters were counted on an end-window type G.M. counter in conjunction with a decade scaler, high voltage unit and a timer and γ -emitters were counted on a γ -ray spectrometer in conjunction with a 3.5 cm \times 3.5 cm NaI(Tl) flat-type detector.

General extraction procedure To a solution (1 ml) of Hg^{II} containing Hg^{II} (1.0 mg) labelled with ^{203}Hg , a 1% ethanolic solution of rhodamine B (5 ml) was added. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 2.0 with dil. HCl and

then equilibrated with nitrobenzene (20 ml) for 4.0 min. Both the organic and the aqueous phases were allowed to separate. An aliquot (2 ml) of each phase was taken for counting on a γ -ray spectrometer at the channel corresponding to the 0.279 MeV photopeak of ^{203}Hg .

This separation procedure was applied for the radiochemical separation of mercury from neutron irradiated targets of environmental samples.

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